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UNDER THE AUSPICES

Radiological
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105 Michalakopoulou str., GR11527, Athens – Greece

Tel.: +30 210 7711673, Fax: +30 210 7711289

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EARLY EXPERIENCE WITH CHEMOEMBOLIZATION OF HEPATOCELLULAR CARCINOMA WITH RADIOPAQUE DRUG-ELUTING MICROSPHERES

Hippocrates Moschouris¹, Theodoros Kiakidis², Andreas Dimakis¹, Aggeliki Papadatou¹, Ioannis Kornezos¹, Katerina Malagari³

1. Radiology Department, General Hospital Tzaneio, Piraeus, Greece
2. Radiology Research Unit, Evgenidion Hospital, Athens, Greece
3. 2nd Department of Radiology, University of Athens, Attikon Hospital, Athens, Greece

Introduction: Radiopaque (RO), drug eluting microspheres (DEMs) represent a recent technological advance in transarterial chemoembolization (TACE) of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC).

Purpose: To present our early clinical experience on the aforementioned field.

Materials and methods: Sixteen HCC patients (13 male, 3 female, age: 52-88 years), not eligible for curative treatment, were retrospectively studied. They were treated with TACE with RO-DEMs (DC-Bead Lumi, BTG), with diameter of 70–150 µm, preloaded with 75mg Doxorubicin/2ml of DEMs. The distribution of RO-DEMs was studied with Digital Radiography (DR) during intervention and with Computed Tomography (CT) immediately post intervention and the next day. Response was evaluated with modified Response Evaluation Criteria in Solid Tumors, on the basis of the findings of Contrast Enhanced Magnetic Resonance (CE-MR), performed one month after each session of TACE and 6 months after the first session. Complications were recorded and graded as per CIRSE Classification System.

Results: A total of 27 TACE sessions were performed (mean: 1.7 sessions per patient) and 28 HCC tumors (n=27 hepatic, and n=1 extrahepatic-adrenal metastasis) with diameter of 30-129mm were embolised with RO-DEMs. Post embolization syndrome (minor, grade 2 complication) was observed in 5/16 patients (31.2%). Six months post treatment initiation, 4/16 patients (25%) had complete response, 5/16 (31.2%) had partial response, 6/16 (37.5%) had stable disease and 1/16 (6.2%) had progressive disease. The varying extent of accumulation of RO-DEMs in the target tumors could be appreciated in all patients with DR during intervention, thus facilitating therapeutic decisions. CT diagnosed complete opacification of 6/28 (21.4%) tumors with RO-DEMs and only these tumors showed complete necrosis on subsequent CE-MR.

Conclusions: TACE of HCC with RO-DEMs appears to have a satisfactory safety and efficacy profile; the straightforward detection of the distribution of the embolic material during and post procedure is an additional advantage with potential clinical relevance.

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GIANT SCULL BASE SCHWANNOMAS ASSOCIATED WITH PONTINE CAPILLARY TELANGIECTASIA

Milos Vukovic^{1,2}, Igor Nosek^{1,2}, Mladen Bjelan³, Dusko Kozić^{1,2}

¹ Center for Imaging Diagnostics, Institute of Oncology of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

² University of Novi Sad Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia

³ Magnetic Resonance Diagnostic Center - MRI System, Zrenjanin, Serbia

Introduction: Neurofibromatosis could be associated with intracranial vascular malformations.

Methods: Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) study was ordered in a 57-year-old woman with known pontine capillary telangiectasia associated with developmental venous anomaly, detected 20 years before. Right tympanoplasty has been several times performed due to conductive hearing impairment,

without positive outcome. Paresis of right hypoglossal nerve, gustatory dysfunction, paresis of the ipsilateral laryngeal recurrent nerve and right shoulder pain were the main complaints.

Results: Apart from pontine vascular malformation, MRI revealed the presence of giant masses, consistent with schwannomas within the right infratemporal fossa, affecting the branch of the mandibular nerve, innervating musculus tensor tympani and veli palatini, with consequent fluid within the tympanic cavity and right mastoid cells. Schwannoma of the ipsilateral jugular foramen was also found, explaining the symptoms of IX-XII cranial nerves dysfunction. These schwannomas were not evident on retrospective evaluation of prior MRI scans.

Conclusion: Vascular malformations of the brain might be associated with schwannomas of the skull base, however the tumors could appear decades after.

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THE ROLE OF MR SPECTROSCOPY IN DIFFERENTIATION OF METASTATIC BRAIN LESIONS FROM OTHER TUMORS - A CASE REPORT

Mladen Bjelan, Stefan Stojanoski, Jasmina Boban, Kristina Ivosevic, Dusko Kozic
 University of Novi Sad Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia

Introduction. Solitary brain lesions may have rather atypical imaging characteristics.

Purpose: The aim of this report is to present the role of MR spectroscopy (MRS) in differentiation of atypical brain masses.

Report: Magnetic resonance imaging and MRS were ordered in a 55-year-old man with a history of first seizure in his life. A dural-based mass, hypointense on T2W sequence, measuring 45mm in greatest diameter, was evident in right frontal parafalcine area, showing no significant postcontrast enhancement. Diffusion weighted imaging was inconclusive. Typical enhancement for either meningioma or metastatic lesion was not evident. Primary brain tumor was not considered due to extraaxial localization of the mass. No perifocal vasogenic edema was noted. High choline and lipid concentrations were detected on single voxel MRS sequences with long and short echo, typical for metastatic lesions. The mass was surgically removed. Neuroendocrine lung tumor was the primary source of malignant disorder. Disseminated disease was later evident on positron emission tomography.

Conclusion: Non-enhancing brain metastases are very rare. Both short and long echo MRS may markedly improve the diagnostic accuracy in such circumstances.

